

Proeseeca peringueyi Long-tongued fly

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Insect

Size: Its body is about 16-21 mm, and its proboscis (tongue) is 20-47mm long.

Distribution:

Its range is in south-western Africa, specifically extreme southwestern Namibia through the western part of Northern Cape Province in South Africa (Namaqualand), and into the northwestern portion of the Western Cape Province. Key areas of high diversity include the Kamieskroon area of Namaqualand and the Pakhuis Mountains in the Western Cape.

Importance:

The Long-tongued fly is important ecologically. It is a keystone pollinator for a whole guild of long-tubed, vividly colored flowers. Through its specialized morphology and behavior, it facilitates efficient and species-specific pollination, supports plant biodiversity, and likely drives co-evolution in its plant partners.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 34.81 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 1.09 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.56 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.0% [Single: 94.7%, Duplicated: 4.2%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 534.11 kilobases

Contig number: 11 763

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